

Horizon Europe

Data Management Plan

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DMP version: 1.1

The Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement requires that a data management plan ('DMP') is established and regularly updated. The use of this template is recommended for Horizon Europe beneficiaries. In completing the sections of the template the requirements for research data management of Horizon Europe as described in article 17 and analysed in the Annotated Grant Agreement, article 17, must be addressed.

1. Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data, and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

I will re-use data from the ROSSIO Controlled vocabularies in Social Sciences, Arts, and Humanities (<http://www.arquivos.pt/>) to create classes of the REWIND Ontology associated with European cultural heritage items. These services are managed by the Centre for Digital Development of Research of NOVA FCSH and are made available to its academic community and the partners of ROSSIO Infrastructure (<http://www.arquivos.pt/pub/en/>). In the case of places, I will use the GeoNames gazetteer (<https://www.geonames.org/>) because it is a geographical database covering all countries and contains over eleven million placenames available under a Creative Commons Attribution licence. I will use the Virtual International Authority File (VIAF) (<https://viaf.org/>) for modelling data related to persons and institutions because it is an international authority system of reference. In addition, it is a joint project of several national libraries and is operated by the Online Computer Library Center. I also use the ORCID (<https://orcid.org/>) URIs to identify the digital editor. And I will use the unique identifier of a data item on Wikidata (QID) (<https://www.wikidata.org/>) to identify the different elements of European cultural heritage mentioned in the travel books studied.

On the other hand, the REWIND ontology is based on the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (<https://www.cidoc-crm.org/>). However, I also reuse some properties from the Europeana Data Model (<https://pro.europeana.eu/page/edm-documentation>). I use the RDA Registry (<http://www.rdaregistry.info/>) because it is a data model for bibliographic description that provides standards to link biographic data.

Finally, I will use the Dublin Core (<https://www.dublincore.org/>) metadata model to describe digital and physical resources used in the REWIND Project.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

- REWIND project readme files will be saved in TXT format (.txt)
- Geo-semantically annotated digital editions of travel books will be submitted in XML-TEI format (.xml)
- REWIND project encoding and mapping guidelines documentation will be preserved using PDF/A format (.pdf).
- REWIND project ontology will be stored in OWL format (.owl).
- REWIND project podcast episodes will be saved in MP3 format (.mp3).
- REWIND project raster images will be stored in PNG format (.png)
- REWIND project vectorial images will be stored in SVG format (.svg)

- REWIND project sentiment analysis scripts in Python will be created in open-source Jupyter Notebook format (.ipynb).
- REWIND project sentiment analysis scripts in R will be created in R format (.r).

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

REWIND project data will be stored following the FAIR principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability because one of the objectives of the project is to contribute to Open Science. REWIND propose a methodology based on open source that can be replicated easily. So, all the data generated for the project will be shared using a Creative Common Licence of CC BY-NC 4.0. In addition, the datasets produced for the project will be connected and integrated into the semantic web because REWIND re-uses data from ROSSIO Infrastructure, GeoNames, VIAF, ORCID, Dublin Core, and CIDOC-CRM to harmonise and standardise the information. The metadata associated with the data and deliverables of the project will be published under the licence CC0. In this way, the REWIND project aims to promote transparent and accessible knowledge that is shared and developed through collaborative networks.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The expected size of the data that I intend to generate has a size of 50GB.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The origin of the data generated for REWIND project is the following travel literature sources:

- C. Matto: *Viaje de recreo: España, Francia, Inglaterra, Italia, Suiza, Alemania* (Valencia: F. Sempere, 1909). Available at Biblioteca Virtual Cervantes: <https://www.cervantesvirtual.com/nd/ark:/59851/bmcv1v0>
- I. Carrasquilla: *Impresiones de viaje escritas por una abuela para sus nietos* (Universidad EAFIT, 2011). Available at Universidad EAFIT (Editorial EAFIT): <https://www.eafit.edu.co/cultura-eafit/fondo-editorial/colecciones/Paginas/impresiones-viaje.aspx>
- I. Echeverría: *Entre dos siglos* (Santiago de Chile: Ediciones Ercilla, 1937). Available at Biblioteca Nacional de Chile: <https://www.memoriachilena.gob.cl/602/w3-article-8313.html>
- M. E. Camarillo: *Brujas, Lisboa, Madrid* (Madrid: Espasa Calpe, 1930). Available at Decimonónicas: Catálogo de autoras mexicanas del siglo XIX: https://drive.google.com/file/d/15pe2S7sk6_ePOsBP8LyLTHTB7uvfemWM/view
- Z. A. Cáceres: *Oasis de arte* (Paris: Garnier Hermanos, 1911). Available at Bibliothèque nationale de France – Gallica: <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k999643v>

The provenance of the data reuse for the REWIND project is as follows:

- URIs from ROSSIO Controlled vocabularies in social sciences, arts, and humanities (<http://www.arquivos.pt/>). Vocab ROSSIO allows users to browse and search concepts and terms in the vocabularies, which are also accessible to machines as linked data. In

addition, Vocab ROSSIO allows describing datasets to be published in open access, following the FAIR principles, which include using documented and resolvable vocabularies accessible using unique and persistent identifiers to enable interoperability with other datasets published on the Web.

- URIs from CIDOC-CRM (<https://www.cidoc-crm.org/>), Europeana Data Model (<https://pro.europeana.eu/page/edm-documentation>) and RDA Registry (<http://www.rdaregistry.info/>) related to classes and properties included in the REWIND Ontology.
- Geographical coordinates from GeoNames Gazetteer (<https://www.geonames.org/>) to geolocate the places mentioned in the travel books studied.
- URIs from VIAF (<https://viaf.org/>) to reference the persons and institutions mentioned in the travel books studied.
- URIs from ORCID (<https://orcid.org/>) to identify the digital editor.
- Unique identifier of a data item from Wikidata (QID) (<https://www.wikidata.org/>) to identify the different elements of European cultural heritage mentioned in the travel books studied.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The benefits of this initiative are evident at different levels because it does not consist exclusively of an academic exercise in literary-historical geography but also a social initiative applicable to the improvement of the city's cultural policy, and with possible implementation in the tourism economic sector. Making all REWIND project results freely available on the Internet via Open Access under Creative Commons License will intensify the research impact. Furthermore, in this way, easy access to research outputs and dissemination of the results is favoured, enabling stakeholders within and beyond the academy to consult and re-use the project material for their purposes.

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Geo-semantically annotated digital editions of travel books will be attributed to a DOI.

The REWIND project ontology's classes, properties and instances will have a URI.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Yes, because the REWIND project uses the Dublin Core (<https://www.dublincore.org/>) and Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) (<https://tei-c.org/>) protocols to provide metadata of data and deliverables of the project. These metadata systems are designed for interoperability based on Semantic Web and Linked Data principles.

In the geo-semantically annotated digital editions, I will include metadata referring to the

original source, title, author, publication date, place of publication, language, and digital editor.

In the REWIND Ontology, I will include the metadata of the identifier, creator, date, description, language, source and title.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Yes, because the REWIND project is based on structured data, which processing and creation are time-consuming since semantic annotation relies heavily on human analysis. So, the geo-semantic annotation, and the design of the ontological modelling are according to the deep data concept. Furthermore, it follows the FAIR principles and uses data standardisation models, such as the proposal of the Text Encoding Initiative (<https://tei-c.org/>) for the expression of texts in digital format or the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (<https://www.cidoc-crm.org/>) to integrate into the field of cultural heritage the representation of cultural heritage items mentioned in the travel literature analysed by REWIND project.

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes, because the REWIND project follows the FAIR principles and uses standardised protocols to describe the metadata of the data and deliverables of the project.

The geo-semantically annotated digital edition metadata will be created in compliance with the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) (<https://tei-c.org/>) standards. So, the header, represented by a <teiHeader> element, contains the metadata that describes the document. The metadata used in the REWIND project are grouped into the <fileDesc> element, which contains a full bibliographic description of the electronic file

The metadata of the REWIND Ontology will be published following the Dublin Core (<https://www.dublincore.org/>) guidelines to describe the information about each element of the European cultural heritage contained in the travel books studied by the project.

2.2 Making data accessible

Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

The REWIND project dataset will be stored in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>), a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN). It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefacts.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Not applicable.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes, for each submission, Zenodo mints a persistent digital object identifier (DOI), making the

stored items easily citeable.

Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

All the datasets of the REWIND project will be shared in open access to contribute to the dissemination and accessibility of data, publication, scripts, and maps, among others, to all levels of society.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Not applicable.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Yes, because all the datasets of the REWIND project follow the FAIR principles and are created based on standardised models of encoding and mapping data proposed by TEI (<https://tei-c.org/>) and Dublin Core (<https://www.dublincore.org/>).

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

Not applicable.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Not applicable.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Not applicable.

Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes, the metadata associated with the data and deliverables of the project will be published under a public domain dedication CC0. In addition, following the Dublin Core (<https://www.dublincore.org/>) guidelines style basis of Semantic Web or Linked Data principles, the metadata uses URIs as global identifiers both for the things described by the metadata and for the terms used to describe them (vocabularies).

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to

remain available after data is no longer available?

Zenodo guarantees that the data is stored safely for the future in CERN’s Data Centre for as long as CERN exists, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes, the REWIND project will produce readme files about information related to the project's dataset. So, for example, the readme file associated with the REWIND Ontology will have a link to direct to Protégé open source software (<https://protege.stanford.edu/>).

The REWIND project only uses open-source code software such as Protégé (<https://protege.stanford.edu/>), Visual Studio Code (<https://code.visualstudio.com/>), R Studio (<https://posit.co/products/open-source/rstudio/>), QGIS (<https://qgis.org/>), and Audacity (<https://www.audacityteam.org/>) because the aim of the proposed methodology is that it can be used by both the scientific community and the general public to develop other projects.

2.3 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

The REWIND project re-uses data from ROSSIO Controlled vocabularies in Social Sciences, Arts, and Humanities (<http://www.arquivos.pt/>), GeoNames (<https://www.geonames.org/>), VIAF (<https://viaf.org/>), ORCID (<https://orcid.org/>) and WIKIDATA (<https://www.wikidata.org/>) to create the digital geo-semantically annotated digital editions of the travel books studied and the REWIND Ontology.

The REWIND project re-uses classes and properties from CIDOC-CRM (<https://www.cidoc-crm.org/>), Europeana Data Model (<https://pro.europeana.eu/page/edm-documentation>) and RDA Registry (<http://www.rdaregistry.info/>) and metadata from the DC (<https://www.dublincore.org/>) to configure the REWIND Ontology.

The REWIND project follows the encoding standards in XML proposed by TEI (<https://tei-c.org/>) to create the digital geo-semantically annotated digital editions of the travel books studied.

Regarding the formats, the data of the REWIND project will only be stored in a perdurable format:

Format	Extension	Norma
Text	.txt	
	PDF/A	Norma ISO 19005
	.pdf	
	.xml	W3C

Image	.png	Norma ISO/IEC 15948
Audio	.mp3	Norma ISO 11172
Ontology	.owl	W3C
Code (script)	.r	
	.ipynb	

I will follow the interoperability proposal of the Dublin Core style (<https://www.dublincore.org/>). This protocol recommends practice such as using a controlled vocabulary where it is available. So, the REWIND project uses different controlled vocabularies for encoding and mapping the travel literature source analysed.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

Not applicable.

Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Yes. The REWIND Ontology contains URIs referencing classes and properties from other ontologies and controlled vocabularies such as CIDOC-CRM, EDM, GeoNames, ROSSIO or VIAF. In addition, all the ontology instances referring to European cultural heritage have a code to be used as a reference in the geo-semantically encoding travel books.

2.4 Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

REWIND project encoding guidelines documentation explains the methodology used to produce the geo-semantically annotated digital editions of travel books following the Text Initiative Encoding standards. In addition, the geo-semantically annotated digital editions of travel books have a declaration that informs about the origin of the source, the author of the digital edition, the creation data, and the protocol followed to create it.

REWIND project mapping guidelines documentation explains how the ontology is built following the data model proposed by CIDOC-CRM and using classes and properties from RDA Registry (<http://www.rdaregistry.info/>) and Dublin Core (<https://www.dublincore.org/>).

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

REWIND project sentiment analysis scripts will have an associated readme introduction and comments to explain how the code works.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Yes, because the REWIND project dataset will be shared by the Creative Common Licence of CC BY-NC 4.0 (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/>).

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes, because the REWIND project dataset will be available in Zenodo open repository.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Yes, because the REWIND project follows codification standards, both for producing and storing data, as explained in the previous sections.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

The documentation of the REWIND project encoding and mapping guidelines will be preserved using PDF/A format (.pdf) and shared so that other projects can apply the methodology.

REWIND project podcast episodes will be saved in MP3 format (.mp3) and stored in Zenodo. In addition, I will share the audio files on the project website and Spotify.

The panels of the exhibition “Cultural Heritage through the Literature of early 20th century Latin American women authors” will be shown at the University NOVA Library. I will also store the textual content of the panels in TXT format (.txt).

4. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) is an open repository free to upload and free to access. In this

way, Zenodo makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable, and discoverable long-term.

We will invest in an external hard drive.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

Not applicable.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The researcher will have overall responsibility for data management during the project. I will be assisted by the Research Support Office and the Núcleo de Desenvolvimento Digital da Investigação.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

The datasets resulting from the research will be preserved in open and durable formats in the open-access repository Zenodo. This free and secure repository will safeguard the information for at least twenty years.

5. Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery and secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

All data files are stored in CERN Data Centres, primarily in Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, backed up to tape nightly. In addition, I will schedule a backup twice a month on an external hard drive.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes, the REWIND project dataset and documentation will be stored in Zenodo open repository, built and operated by CERN. Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

6. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethical issues were identified while preparing the proposal for the REWIND project. Regarding intellectual property rights, the books that make up the textual corpus are out of copyright, and digitised versions are available via public digital libraries: Biblioteca Nacional de España, Repositorio Institucional Universidad EAFIT, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, and Biblioteca Nacional de Chile.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

It is not applicable because personal or sensitive data will not be processed.

7. Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

No, I will not make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management.